

Determination of Genetic Diversity of Some Soybean Genotypes Through SCoT MarkersYeter ÇİLESİZ^{1*} ¹ Sivas University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Technology, Department of Field Crops, Sivas, Türkiye*Corresponding author: ycilesiz@sivas.edu.tr

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the genetic diversity among 18 soybean (*Glycine max* L.) genotypes (13 breeding lines and 5 commercial varieties). For this purpose, a total of 36 SCoT (Start Codon Targeted) primers were screened in the samples and 12 primers showing high levels of polymorphism were selected for further analysis. PCR amplification using these primers yielded 115 scorable bands, 83 of which were polymorphic, resulting in a high polymorphism rate of 72.18%. With their high polymorphism rates and PIC values, SCoT-6 and SCoT-26 stand out as suitable for evaluation in breeding applications such as parental selection. The generated UPGMA dendrogram divided the genotypes into two main clusters. In particular, the G-3 genotype exhibited the lowest similarity (0.571) compared to G-14, indicating that this genotype could be a genetically distinct resource for expanding the breeding pool. In contrast, the G-10 and G-11 genotypes exhibited the highest genetic similarity (0.923), reflecting their similar genetic background. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Clustering (UPGMA) results were found to be mutually supportive. The observed genetic variation within and between groups demonstrates the effectiveness of SCoT markers in distinguishing soybean genotypes and highlights the presence of diverse allelic sources. These findings provide valuable molecular information for sustainable soybean breeding efforts aimed at improving parental selection, heterotic group formation, productivity, adaptation, and genetic resistance.

Keywords: *Glycine max*, genetic characterization, scot, molecular markers

1. Introduction

Soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.) is an important legume species cultivated widely worldwide, both in the food and feed industries, and has a high protein and oil content (Li et al., 2010; Çilesiz et al., 2025a). It is also used in biodiesel production and various industrial applications. Its nitrogen-fixing properties, which increase soil fertility, make it a popular choice in sustainable agricultural systems (Abebe et al., 2021). Although soybean production is relatively limited in Turkey, it is increasingly being considered as an alternative crop in agricultural production patterns due to factors such as climate change, the need for diversity in crop patterns, and the reduction of fallow land (Rayan and Osman, 2019; Karaköy et al., 2024; Sayed et al., 2024). Today, soybean cultivation faces numerous production challenges, including a narrow genetic base, climatic stresses, and susceptibility to diseases and pests. These problems highlight the need to conserve existing genetic resources, identify genetic differences among varieties, and develop new varieties based on extensive genetic variation (Kumawat et al., 2015; Çilesiz et al., 2025b). Traditional phenotypic assessment methods are insufficient for objectively analyzing genetic diversity due to their high sensitivity to environmental factors. This necessitates the use of more precise and reliable molecular analysis techniques in modern plant breeding programs (Kachare et al., 2020; Baloch et al., 2022; Küçük et al., 2024). In recent years, the identification of genetic resources, the quantitative assessment of variation levels, and the characterization of breeding materials have been more effectively achieved thanks to DNA-based molecular markers (Wang et al., 2015; Sevindik et al., 2023; Ovalıoğlu and Çilesiz, 2025). These markers reveal genetic differences directly at the DNA level, independent of environmental influences, allowing for more accurate analysis of parameters such as genetic similarity, relatedness, and population structure (Ning et al., 2016; Ouchar et al., 2023; Tan and Arabacı, 2024; Oral et al., 2024). In this context, SCoT markers, developed for genetic analyses, have

been widely used in many plant species in recent years due to their association with coding regions, high polymorphism, and high reproducibility (Shimira et al., 2021; Ovalıoğlu and Çilesiz, 2025). SCoT markers provide more reliable results than random markers such as ISSR and RAPD due to their association with coding regions, high polymorphism, and strong reproducibility. While RAPD and ISSR markers are inexpensive and rapid, they have the disadvantages of low reproducibility and limited genome coverage. SSR markers, on the other hand, are highly informative but costly and time-consuming to develop. In contrast, SCoT markers offer an effective alternative in breeding studies due to their low cost, practical applicability, and wide application (Sevindik et al., 2024; Çetin et al., 2025). In this study, genetic diversity analyses were conducted using SCoT markers on 13 soybean lines and 5 commercial varieties (Mersoy, ANP 2018, Traksoy, Viktoria, and Arısoy) developed from crosses conducted in accordance with breeding objectives in the soybean breeding program conducted at the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Technologies, Sivas University of Science and Technology. The primary objective of the study was to reveal the genetic variation among these genotypes, quantitatively assess genetic similarities and relationships, and establish a scientific basis for genetic resources that can be used in breeding programs. The findings are expected to make significant contributions to parental selection and the determination of sustainable strategies in soybean breeding.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Plant materials and genomic DNA isolation

In this study, 13 soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.) lines developed through hybridizations carried out in accordance with breeding objectives within the ongoing soybean breeding program at the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Technologies, Sivas University of Science and Technology and 5 commercial cultivars (Mersoy, ANP 2018, Traksoy, Victoria, Arısoy) were used as

materials (Table 1). Within the scope of the soybean (*Glycine max* L.) breeding program carried out under the ecological conditions of Sivas, registered cultivars such as Arisoy, Blaze, Nova, May 5312, SA-88, Bravo, Adasoy, Traksoy, Ataem-7, Lider, Mersoy, and Viktoria were used as parental material. Considering the morphological, phenological and agronomic characteristics of these cultivars, different hybrid combinations were developed with the aim of combining the

targeted traits, including earliness, high yield, wide adaptability and tolerance/resistance to diseases and abiotic stress conditions. DNA extraction from the leaves of soybean samples was performed using the CTAB protocol as described by Doyle and Doyle (1990). The concentrations of stock DNA were measured using a MaestroNano Pro Spectrophotometer (MN913A, MaestroGen) and the DNA samples were subsequently diluted to a final concentration of 5 ng μL^{-1} .

Table 1. Details of soybean genotypes used in the study

Genotype code	Name	Species name
G1	Line4	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G2	Line7	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G3	Line18	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G4	Line24	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G5	Line35	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G6	Line40	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G7	Line60	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G8	Line66	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G9	Line70	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G10	Line77	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G11	Line89	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G12	Line110	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G13	Line127	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merr.
G14	Mersoy	Commercial variety
G15	ANP 2018	Commercial variety
G16	Traksoy	Commercial variety
G17	Victoria	Commercial variety
G18	Arisoy	Commercial variety

2.2. SCoT marker assay

The SCoT primers selected for PCR amplification and the corresponding PCR cycling conditions are provided in Table 2. The PCR reaction mixture consisted of 4 μL of DNA (20 ng), 1 μL of primer, 10 μL of PCR master mix (Eco Tech, Cat No: ET5) and 10 μL of dH₂O. For electrophoresis of the PCR products, a 2% agarose gel prepared in Tris-

borate-EDTA buffer was used. DNA bands were visualized under UV light. A total of 36 SCoT primers were initially screened across the samples and 12 primers exhibiting polymorphic patterns were selected for further analysis (Table 2). In the selected 12 primers, the number of polymorphic bands was high and the band intensity was at the desired level and clear. The other primers did not exhibit these characteristics.

Table 2. SCoT primers used for PCR amplification

SCoT primers code	DNA Sequences (5'-3')	%GC	Tm °C	PCR Amplification
SCoT-6	CAACAATGGCTACCACGC	56	56	
SCoT-12	ACGACATGGCGACCAACG	61	58	
SCoT-14	ACGACATGGCGACCACGC	67	61	
SCoT-17	ACCATGGCTACCACCGAG	61	58	94 °C - 3 min
SCoT-19	ACCATGGCTACCACCGGC	67	61	94 °C - 1 min
SCoT-20	ACCATGGCTACCACCGCG	67	61	56-61 °C 1 min
SCoT-21	ACGACATGGCGACCCACA	61	58	72 °C - 1 min
SCoT-23	CACCATGGCTACCACCAG	61	58	72 °C - 10 min
SCoT-24	CACCATGGCTACCACCAT	56	56	35 cycles
SCoT-26	ACCATGGCTACCACCGTC	61	58	
SCoT-34	ACCATGGCTACCACCGCA	61	58	
SCoT-36	GCAACAATGGCTACCACC	56	56	

2.3. Statistical analysis

The bands obtained from the PCR analysis were scored as 1 for presence and 0 for absence. Diversity parameters such as effective number of alleles, gene diversity and Shannon diversity index as well as Nei's genetic distance were calculated using POPGENE ver. 1.32 software (<https://sites.ualberta.ca/~fyeh/popgene.html>) (Yeh et al., 2000). The mean polymorphism information contents (PIC) of each SCoT primer were deduced using the following formula (equation 1) (Roldan-Ruiz et al., 2000):

$$PIC = 2f_i(1-f_i) \quad (1)$$

where PIC is the polymorphic information content, f_i represents the frequency of presence of the band and $1 - f_i$ shows the absence of the band. A dendrogram based on Jaccard's similarity coefficients was generated using the

Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic Mean (UPGMA) in MVSP 3.22 software (Kovach, 2007). Application of MVSP 3.22 to the SCoT molecular data enabled the construction of a genetic similarity matrix. In addition, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed using MVSP 3.22 to assess the genetic relationships among soybean genotypes.

3. Results and Discussion

In this study, the genetic diversity of 13 soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.) lines developed through hybridizations carried out in accordance with breeding objectives within the ongoing soybean breeding program at the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Technologies, Sivas University of Science and Technology, along with 5 commercial cultivars (Mersoy, ANP 2018, Traksoy, Victoria, Arisoy), was evaluated using SCoT markers.

Table 3. 12 primers used for SCoT assay, number of total and polymorphic bands and diversity parameters

SCoT primers code	Number of bands		Diversity parameter				
	Polymorphic bands	Total bands	P%	ne	h	I	PIC
SCoT-6	10	10	100	1.68	0.39	0.57	0.39
SCoT-12	8	11	73	1.50	0.29	0.42	0.29
SCoT-14	2	6	33	1.32	0.16	0.23	0.16
SCoT-17	6	9	67	1.36	0.24	0.39	0.24
SCoT-19	5	7	71	1.44	0.27	0.42	0.27
SCoT-20	5	9	56	1.33	0.20	0.31	0.20
SCoT-21	10	13	77	1.34	0.20	0.31	0.20
SCoT-23	7	11	64	1.23	0.15	0.25	0.16
SCoT-24	7	12	58	1.40	0.24	0.36	0.24
SCoT-26	9	9	100	1.59	0.35	0.53	0.35
SCoT-34	6	8	75	1.53	0.30	0.46	0.30
SCoT-36	6	10	60	1.29	0.17	0.27	0.17

A total of 115 DNA bands (83 polymorphic/32 monomorphic) were obtained from 12 primers. The polymorphism rate was determined to be 72.18%, and based on this rate, it was determined that SCoT markers can distinguish DNA-level variations with high sensitivity. Table 3 demonstrates that SCoT markers revealed genetic diversity among soybean genotypes with high sensitivity. The highest polymorphism rates were observed in primers SCoT-6 and SCoT-26 (100%), indicating that all bands were polymorphic and thus provided maximum variation among the genotypes. The lowest polymorphism rate was detected in primer SCoT-14 (33%), which can be interpreted as having weak discriminatory power in terms of genetic diversity. In particular, SCoT-6 and SCoT-26, with their high polymorphism rates and PIC values, stand out as the most useful primers for future genetic diversity studies and breeding applications such as parent selection. The highest effective number of alleles (ne) was observed in primers SCoT-6 (1.68) and SCoT-26 (1.59), indicating a high level of allelic diversity. The primers with the highest genetic diversity (h) values were SCoT-6 (0.39) and SCoT-26 (0.35), showing that these primers revealed genetic differences more effectively. For Shannon's index (I), the highest values

were again recorded in SCoT-6 (0.57) and SCoT-26 (0.53), reflecting a high degree of information richness and diversity. Regarding the Polymorphic Information Content (PIC), the highest discriminatory power was found in primers SCoT-6 (0.39) and SCoT-26 (0.35), while the lowest PIC value was observed in SCoT-14 (0.16) (Table 3). In a study conducted by Rayan and Osman (2019) using the SCoT technique, 11 primers were used and a total of 106 bands (52 polymorphic and 54 monomorphic) were obtained. The polymorphism rate was determined to be 49.11%. The dendrogram created by the researchers observed that the varieties were divided into two main clusters. In a study conducted with 28 soybean genotypes, SCoT markers were used and a total of 260 DNA bands were generated, with an average of 7.03 bands per primer. Among the 37 primers used, SCoT 33 and SCoT 65 exhibited the highest polymorphism, each producing 10 polymorphic amplification products. The lowest number of polymorphic fragments (2) was detected by primers SCoT 8, SCoT 14, SCoT 19 and SCoT 31. Of the 260 amplified bands, 200 (77.27%) were polymorphic, with an average of 5.41 polymorphic bands per primer (Vivodík et al., 2023).

Figure 1. UPGMA dendrogram of genetic similarity between SCoT markers 13 soybean lines and 5 commercial cultivars

The dendrogram constructed based on the Jaccard similarity coefficient using the UPGMA (Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic Mean) method divided the genotypes into two main groups (Figure 1).

Group A consists solely of genotype G-3, indicating that this genotype possesses a high level of genetic divergence compared to the others (Table 4).

Table 4. Pairwise genetic distance matrix obtained from 12 SCoT primers

Group 1	Group 2	Similarity	Objects in group
G-10	G-11	0.923	2
G-9	Node 1	0.895	3
G-8	Node 2	0.873	4
G-2	Node 3	0.848	5
G-4	G-5	0.840	2
Node 4	Node 5	0.822	7
Node 6	G-12	0.809	8
G-16	G-17	0.802	2
Node 7	G-14	0.800	9
Node 8	G-18	0.778	3
G-7	G-13	0.770	2
G-15	Node 10	0.725	4
Node 9	Node 11	0.705	11
Node 13	Node 12	0.662	15
G-1	G-6	0.650	2
Node 15	Node 14	0.616	17
Node 16	G-3	0.571	18

The genetic similarity between G-3 and Node-16 is only 0.571, which represents the lowest similarity coefficient observed in this study. In the hierarchical clustering process, a node represents a newly formed composite

group that emerges when two groups (such as individuals or previously merged subgroups) are combined at a certain level of similarity defining the intermediate junctions in the dendrogram (Figure 1, Table 4). These nodes

indicate that previously merged genotypes or groups are further joined with other individuals or nodes at a specific level of similarity (Clevenger et al., 2015). Such a distant genetic relationship suggests that G-3 may carry rare or distinct alleles and therefore may serve as a valuable genetic resource for creating heterotic combinations in breeding programs. Group B is further divided into two subgroups: B1 and B2. The B1 subgroup includes genotypes G-1 and G-6, whereas the B2 subgroup exhibits a more heterogeneous structure and is further divided into two clusters: "a" (commercial cultivars: G-15, G-16, G-17, G-18) and "b" (other lines: G-2, G-4, G-5, G-7, G-8, G-9, G-10, G-11, G-12, G-14). This structural separation reflects the genetic differentiation based on the origin of the materials used in the study, which include both gene bank-derived lines and commercial cultivars. Vivodík et al. (2023) constructed a dendrogram illustrating the genetic relationships among soybean genotypes. The hierarchical cluster analysis revealed that the soybean genotypes were divided into four main clusters. The markers used in this study produced a large number of polymorphic bands that were distinctive among the different cultivars and found to be suitable as molecular markers for differentiating them at the molecular level. The obtained data demonstrated that the SCoT technique can be effectively used for the identification and differentiation of soybean genotypes. Nosair (2016) analyzed the genetic diversity of nine species belonging to the Fabaceae family (*Vicia faba*, *Trigonella foenum-graecum*, *Cicer arietinum*, *Lens culinaris*, *Glycine max*, *Lupinus termis*, *Vigna unguiculata*, *Phaseolus vulgaris* and *Pisum sativum*) using SCoT markers. A total of 183 bands were produced, with a polymorphism rate of 93.99%. The dendrogram analysis also revealed genetic variation among the nine species. This study demonstrated that the SCoT marker system is an effective method for assessing genetic diversity in various legume species. Çilesiz (2025a) obtained a total of 49 bands using RAPD primers in sugar beet samples, 40 of which were identified as polymorphic, corresponding to a

polymorphism level of 81.6%. Çilesiz (2025b) evaluated the diversity in sugar beet samples using SCoT primers. A total of 152 bands were obtained from 15 markers, 102 of which were identified as polymorphic, with an average of 10.13 bands per primer. The polymorphism rate was determined to be 67.11%. Hromadová et al. (2022) analyzed the genetic diversity among 34 common bean genotypes using 5 SCoT markers. A total of 82 DNA bands were amplified, of which 66 were polymorphic, resulting in an average of 11 polymorphic bands per primer. The highest number of polymorphic bands (15) was detected by the SCoT 59 primer. The percentage of polymorphism ranged from 57.17% (SCoT 2) to 78.57% (SCoT 19), with an average calculated at 67.3%. Çilesiz (2025c) evaluated the genetic diversity of 18 walnut genotypes using two different markers: ISSR and RAPD. A total of 72 bands (54 polymorphic; 75.0%) were obtained with nine ISSR primers, and 53 bands (42 polymorphic; 79.2%) were obtained with five RAPD primers. Baloch et al. (2010) obtained 31 and 26 polymorphic bands from ISSR analysis performed with 46 primers in soybean and 47 primers in peanut, respectively. A total of 26 polymorphic amplicons were obtained from soybean. In soybean, the UPGMA dendrogram clustered all cultivars into the same group, except for the 'Yeşilsoy' cultivar, which was placed in a separate group. Sönmez and Çilesiz (2025) obtained a total of 119 bands from 12 SCoT primers in their study on grapes. Among these, 83 were polymorphic bands, resulting in a polymorphism rate of 69.74%. According to the UPGMA dendrogram and the correlation matrix generated from the SCoT molecular data, the lowest genetic similarity (0.382) was observed between genotypes G6 and G38, while the highest similarity (0.786) was found between genotypes G37 and G39. Temrel and Çilesiz (2025) obtained a total of 169 bands from 14 SCoT primers in thyme. Among these, 141 were polymorphic bands, resulting in a polymorphism rate of 83.43%. According to the UPGMA dendrogram and the correlation matrix generated from the SCoT molecular data, the lowest genetic similarity (0.326) was

observed between samples G12 and G17, while the highest similarity (0.854) was found between G8 and G10. The highest similarity coefficient in the dendrogram was found between genotypes G-10 and G-11 (0.923) (Table 4). This close genetic relationship suggests that these genotypes may share a common selection history or possess a similar genetic background. These genotypes could be candidates for genetic fidelity and phenotypic uniformity studies and may be particularly useful in quality and purity assessments during cultivar registration processes. Similarly, genotypes G-4 and G-5 also exhibit a high level of genetic similarity with a coefficient of 0.840 and can be considered within the same selection group (Table 4).

To provide a more comprehensive and dimensionally reduced analysis of genetic diversity, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted and yielded findings that support the results of the UPGMA clustering. The PCA analysis demonstrated that genetically similar genotypes were positioned closely on the coordinate plane, whereas genetically distant ones were distributed along distinct axes. G-10 and G-11, which showed the highest similarity in the UPGMA analysis, were also located near each other in the PCA plot (Figure 2). The first three principal components accounted for a large proportion of the total variance, indicating that the major genetic differences among the genotypes are concentrated along these axes. In the PCA analysis, the first component (Axis 1) explained 34.7% of the genetic variance and separated the genotypes into two main groups.

The second component (Axis 2), accounting for 21.3% of the variance, contributed to the differentiation of certain genotypes, particularly G-1, G-6, and G-9. Together, the two axes represented 56.0% of the genetic variation among the genotypes. The wide dispersion of genotypes in the PCA plot reflects a high level of genetic diversity within the studied material and suggests the presence of subpopulations (Figure 2). These subgroups may have formed due to ecotypic differentiation, adaptation processes, or breeding history. Furthermore, this structural variation provides a critical foundation for future genome-wide association studies (GWAS), enabling accurate assessment of population structure. The high level of genetic diversity identified in this study is of great significance for sustainable soybean breeding programs. Genetically similar genotypes (G-10 and G-11) can be utilized in line purification, development of stable lines, and phenotypic stability analyses. On the other hand, genetically distant genotypes (G-3 and G-14) can be employed in hybrid breeding to form heterotic combinations. Such genotypes are strategically important for enhancing resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses, increasing yield potential, and broadening adaptation capacity. Moreover, the placement of commercial cultivars (G-15, G-16, G-17 and G-18) within different subgroups indicates that these varieties have been derived from distinct genetic pools and that their genetic backgrounds have developed independently. This diversity allows the current commercial cultivars to be used complementarily in future hybridization programs.

Figure 2. SCoT markers principal component analyses of samples using MVSP 3.22 software (Kovach Computing Services, Pentraeth, Wales, UK)

5. Conclusion

The study concluded that SCoT markers are an effective and reliable method for determining genetic diversity among soybean genotypes. The high polymorphism level obtained at 72.18% demonstrates the diversity among our genotypes and the richness of variation at the molecular level. Genetic relationships were comprehensively assessed using both UPGMA cluster analysis and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The results of these two analytical methods were largely consistent, demonstrating strong agreement in grouping the genotypes. We believe that the findings will facilitate the transfer of targeted traits, such as high yield, disease resistance, and abiotic stress tolerance, to new varieties and provide a solid scientific basis for sustainable strategies in future breeding programs.

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